

Smarandache U-liberal semigroup structure

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Abstract In this paper, Smarandache U-liberal semigroup structure is given. It is shown that a semigroup S is Smarandache U-liberal semigroup if and only if it is a strong semilattice of some rectangular monoids. Consequently, some corresponding results on normal orthocryptou semigroups and normal orthocryptogroups are generalized and extended.

Keywords Smarandache U-liberal semigroup, U -semiabundant semigroups, normal band, rectangular monoid, strong semilattice.

§1. Introduction and preliminaries

In order to generalize regular semigroups, new Green's relations, namely, the Green's $*$ -relations on a semigroup S have been introduced in [1] and [2] as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}^* = \{(a, b) \in S \times S : (\forall x, y \in S^1) ax = ay \Leftrightarrow bx = by\},$$

$$\mathcal{R}^* = \{(a, b) \in S \times S : (\forall x, y \in S^1) xa = ya \Leftrightarrow xb = yb\},$$

$$\mathcal{H}^* = \mathcal{L}^* \cap \mathcal{R}^*, \quad \mathcal{D}^* = \mathcal{L}^* \vee \mathcal{R}^*.$$

In [3], Fountain investigated a class of semigroups called abundant semigroups in which each \mathcal{L}^* -class and each \mathcal{R}^* -class of S contain at least an idempotent. Actually, the class of regular semigroups are properly contained in the class of abundant semigroups.

In 1980, El-Qallali generalized the Green's $*$ -relations to the Green's \sim -relations on a semigroup S in [4] as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathcal{L}} = \{(a, b) \in S \times S : (\forall e \in E(S)) ae = a \Leftrightarrow be = b\},$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}} = \{(a, b) \in S \times S : (\forall e \in E(S)) ea = a \Leftrightarrow eb = b\},$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{H}} = \tilde{\mathcal{L}} \cap \tilde{\mathcal{R}}, \quad \tilde{\mathcal{D}} = \tilde{\mathcal{L}} \vee \tilde{\mathcal{R}}.$$

In his thesis, El-Qallali obtained and studied a much bigger class of semigroups, called semi-abundant semigroup.

After that, many authors study this class of semigroups, and obtain a lot of interesting conclusions and results(see [5],[6],[7] etc.).

In recent years, some scholars have observed that one can pay special attention to a subset U of $E(S)$ instead of the whole set $E(S)$ of a semiabundant semigroup S . In particular, Lawson in [8] noticed that if U is a subset of $E(S)$ of a semiabundant semigroup S then U is perhaps good enough to provide sufficient information for the whole semigroup S . The semigroup S is usually denoted by $S(U)$ and the equivalence relations on $S(U)$ with respect to $U \subseteq E(S)$ can be given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U &= \{(a, b) \in S \times S \mid U_a^r = U_b^r\}, \\ \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U &= \{(a, b) \in S \times S \mid U_a^l = U_b^l\}, \\ \tilde{\mathcal{H}}^U &= \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U \cap \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U, \\ \tilde{\mathcal{Q}}^U &= \{(a, b) \in S \times S \mid U_a = U_b\}, \end{aligned}$$

where $U_a^l = \{u \in U \mid ua = a\}$, $U_a^r = \{u \in U \mid au = a\}$ and $U_a = U_a^l \cap U_a^r = \{u \in U \mid ua = a = au\}$ for any $a \in S$.

A semigroup $S(U)$ is said to be a U -semiabundant semigroup if every $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U$ and every $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U$ -class of $S(U)$ contain at least one element of U respectively. A semigroup $S(U)$ is said to be a U -semi-superabundant semigroup if every $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}^U$ of $S(U)$ contains at least one element of U . In this case, the unique element in $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}_a^U \cap U$ is denoted by a_U° . On the other hand, a semigroup $S(U)$ is called by He in [7] a U -liberal semigroup if every $\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}^U$ -class of S contains an element of U . It is routine to check that a $\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}^U$ -class contains at most one element of U . Denote the unique element in $\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}_a^U \cap U$, if it exists, by a_U° . The structure of Smarandache U -liberal semigroups has also been recently investigated by He in [7].

For a Smarandache U -liberal semigroup $S(U)$, we call the following condition the Ehresmann type condition, in brevity, the ET-condition:

$$(\forall a, b \in S)(ab)_U^0 \mathcal{D}(U) a_U^0 b_U^0,$$

where

$$\mathcal{D}(U) = \{(e, f) \in U \times U \mid (\exists g \in U) e\mathcal{R}g\mathcal{L}f\}.$$

A Smarandache U -liberal semigroup $S(U)$ is called an orthodox U -liberal semigroup if U is a subsemigroup of $S(U)$ and the ET-condition holds on $S(U)$.

In general, unlike the usual Green's relations on a semigroup S , $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U$ is not necessarily a right congruence on S and $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U$ is not necessarily a left congruence on S (see [8]).

We say that a semigroup $S(U)$ satisfies the (CR) condition if $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U$ is a right congruence on S and that $S(U)$ satisfies the (CL) condition if $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U$ is a left congruence on S . If the semigroup $S(U)$ satisfies both the (CR) and (CL) condition, then we say $S(U)$ satisfies the (C) condition.

The studies on the structures of semigroups play an important role in the research of the algebraic theories of semigroups. From [7], it is known that a U -semi-superabundant semigroup $S(U)$ is an orthodox U -liberal semigroup for some $U \subseteq E(S)$ if and only if it is a semilattice of some rectangular monoids, i.e., $S = [Y; S_\alpha(U_\alpha)]$, where $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$ is a rectangular monoid for every $\alpha \in Y$ and $U = \cup_{\alpha \in Y} U_\alpha$ is a subsemigroup of S . Meanwhile, notice that a normal band is a strong semilattice of some rectangular bands. Naturally, we will quote such a question: whether will a normal orthodox U-liberal semigroup $S(U)$ be a strong semilattice of some rectangular monoids?

In this paper, we will consider the question quoted above. Consequently, we show that a semigroup $S(U)$ is a normal orthodox Smarandache U -liberal semigroup if and only if it is a strong semilattice of some rectangular monoids, i.e., $S = [Y; S_\alpha(U_\alpha); \Phi_{\alpha,\beta}]$, where $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$ is a rectangular monoid for every $\alpha \in Y$ and $U = \cup_{\alpha \in Y} U_\alpha$ is a normal band of $S(U)$. Consequently, some corresponding results on normal orthocryptou semigroups and normal orthocryptogroups are generalized and extended.

For notations and terminologies not mentioned in this paper, the reader is referred to [7],[9],[10].

§2. Normal Orthodox U -liberal Semigroups

In this section, we will give a construction of normal orthodox U -liberal semigroups.

Firstly, we recall the following lemmas.

Lemma 2.1. [7] Let \mathcal{F} be one of Green's relations \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R} or \mathcal{H} and $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}^U$ the corresponding Green \sim -relations on the semigroup S . Then, for any $a, b \in S$, we have

(i) $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{F}}^U$ and for $a, b \in \text{Reg}_U(S)$, $a, b \in \tilde{\mathcal{F}}^U$ if and only if $a, b \in \mathcal{F}$, where $\text{Reg}_U(S) = \{a \in S | (\exists e, f \in U) e\mathcal{L}a\mathcal{R}f\}$;

(ii) $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}^U \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{Q}}^U$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}^U$ contains at most one element in U ;

(iii) If $S(U)$ is a U -semi-superabundant semigroup, then $S(U)$ is a Smarandache U -liberal semigroup with $\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}^U = \tilde{\mathcal{H}}^U$.

Lemma 2.2. [7] The following statements are equivalent for a semigroup S :

(i) $S(U)$ is a Smarandache U -liberal semigroup for some $U \subseteq E(S)$ and U itself is a rectangular band;

(ii) $S(U)$ is an orthodox U -liberal semigroup such that U is a rectangular band;

(iii) S is isomorphic to a rectangular monoid.

Lemma 2.3. [7] The following statements are equivalent for a semigroup S :

(i) $S(U)$ is an orthodox U -liberal semigroup for some $U \subseteq E(S)$;

(ii) $S = [Y; S_\alpha(U_\alpha)]$, where $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$ is a rectangular monoid for every $\alpha \in Y$ and $U = \cup_{\alpha \in Y} U_\alpha$ is a subsemigroup of S ;

(iii) $S(U)$ is a U -semi-superabundant semigroup satisfying the (C) condition for some $U \subseteq E(S)$ and U is a subsemigroup of S .

Now, we will give our main theorem.

Theorem 2.4. The following statements are equivalent for a semigroup S :

(i) $S(U)$ is a normal orthodox U -liberal semigroup for some normal band $U \subseteq E(S)$;

(ii) $S(U)$ is a strong semilattice of some rectangular monoids, i.e., $S = [Y; S_\alpha(U_\alpha); \Phi_{\alpha,\beta}]$, where $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$ is a rectangular monoid for every $\alpha \in Y$ and $U = \cup_{\alpha \in Y} U_\alpha$ is a normal band of S ;

(iii) $S(U)$ is a U -semi-superabundant semigroup satisfying the (C) condition for some $U \subseteq E(S)$ and U is a normal band of S .

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii)

Assume that $S(U)$ is a normal orthodoxy U -liberal semigroup for some normal band $U \subseteq E(S)$. Note that $U \subseteq E(S)$ is a normal band, we will have $U = [Y; U_\alpha, f_{\alpha,\beta}]$ or $U = [Y; I_\alpha \times \Lambda_\alpha; \varphi_{\alpha,\beta}, \psi_{\alpha,\beta}]$, where $(i, j)f_{\alpha,\beta} = (i\varphi_{\alpha,\beta}, j\psi_{\alpha,\beta}), (i, j) \in I_\alpha \times \Lambda_\alpha$.

For any $\alpha \in Y$, we form the set $S_\alpha = \{x \in S | x_U^0 \in U_\alpha\}$. Since $S(U)$ satisfies the ET-condition, for all $x \in S_\alpha, y \in S_\beta$, we have $(xy)_U^0 \mathcal{D}(U) x_U^0 y_U^0$. This leads to $xy \in S_{\alpha\beta}$ and hence $S(U) = [Y; S_\alpha(U_\alpha)]$.

Notice that every semigroup $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$ is a Smarandache U_α -liberal semigroup and U_α is a rectangular band. By Lemma 2.2, $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$ is isomorphic to a rectangular monoid. For convenience, we denote $S_\alpha(U_\alpha) = I_\alpha \times T_{U_\alpha} \times \Lambda_\alpha$.

Now, define a mapping,

$$\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} : S_\alpha(U_\alpha) \rightarrow S_\beta(U_\beta),$$

$$(i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha) \rightarrow (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta}, 1_{U_\beta}, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta})(i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha) = (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha).$$

In the following, we will prove that S is a strong semilattice of $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$, i.e., $S = [Y; S_\alpha(U_\alpha); \Phi_{\alpha,\beta}]$.

Firstly, $\Phi_{\alpha,\beta}$ is a homomorphism.

For any $x = (i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha), y = (j_\alpha, v_\alpha, \mu_\alpha) \in S_\alpha (\forall \alpha \geq \beta)$,

$$\begin{aligned} (xy)\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} &= [(i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha)(j_\alpha, v_\alpha, \mu_\alpha)]\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} \\ &= (i_\alpha j_\alpha, u_\alpha v_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \mu_\alpha)\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} \\ &= (i_\alpha, u_\alpha v_\alpha, \mu_\alpha)\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha v_\alpha, \mu_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \mu_\alpha), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} y\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} &= (i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha)\Phi_{\alpha,\beta}(j_\alpha, v_\alpha, \mu_\alpha)\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha)(j_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} j_\alpha, 1_{U_\beta} v_\alpha, \mu_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \mu_\alpha) \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha j_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} j_\alpha, 1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha 1_{U_\beta} v_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha \mu_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \mu_\alpha) \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha v_\alpha, \mu_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \mu_\alpha) \quad (\text{since } U_\alpha \text{ is normal}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $(xy)\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} = x\Phi_{\alpha,\beta} y\Phi_{\alpha,\beta}$.

Secondly, $\Phi_{\alpha,\alpha}$ is an identity mapping.

For any $x = (i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha) \in S_\alpha$, $x\Phi_{\alpha,\alpha} = (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\alpha} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\alpha} u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\alpha} \lambda_\alpha) = (i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha) = x$.

Hence, $\Phi_{\alpha,\alpha}$ is an identity mapping.

Thirdly, notice that for any $x = (i_\alpha, 1_{U_\alpha}, \lambda_\alpha) \in E(S_\alpha) = I_\alpha \times 1_{U_\alpha} \times \Lambda_\alpha, y = (i_\beta, 1_{U_\beta}, \lambda_\beta) \in E(S_\beta) = I_\beta \times 1_{U_\beta} \times \Lambda_\beta, xy \in E(S_{\alpha\beta}) = I_{\alpha\beta} \times 1_{U_{\alpha\beta}} \times \Lambda_{\alpha\beta}$, we can get $1_{U_\alpha} 1_{U_\beta} = 1_{U_{\alpha\beta}}$. Especially, when $\alpha \geq \beta$, we have $1_{U_\alpha} 1_{U_\beta} = 1_{U_{\alpha\beta}} = 1_{U_\beta}$. Now, for any $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in Y (\alpha \geq \beta \geq \gamma)$ and any $x = (i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha) \in S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$, we will have

$$\begin{aligned} (x\Phi_{\alpha,\beta})\Phi_{\beta,\gamma} &= (i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha)\Phi_{\alpha,\beta}\Phi_{\beta,\gamma} = (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha)\Phi_{\beta,\gamma} \\ &= ((i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha) \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha), 1_{U_\gamma} (1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha), (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha) \psi_{\beta,\gamma} (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha)) \\ &= (((i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta})(i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha)) \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha), 1_{U_\gamma} (1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha), (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha) \psi_{\beta,\gamma} (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha)) \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} \varphi_{\beta,\gamma} (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha) \varphi_{\beta,\gamma} (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha), 1_{U_\gamma} (1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha), (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha) \psi_{\beta,\gamma} (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha)) \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\gamma} (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha) \varphi_{\beta,\gamma} (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\beta} i_\alpha), 1_{U_\gamma} (1_{U_\beta} u_\alpha), (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha) \psi_{\beta,\gamma} (\lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\beta} \lambda_\alpha)) \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha,\gamma} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\gamma} u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha,\gamma} \lambda_\alpha) \quad (\text{since } I_\alpha \text{ is a left zero band}) \\ &= x\Phi_{\alpha,\gamma}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, for any $\alpha, \beta \in Y$, $a_\alpha \in S_\alpha$ and $b_\beta \in S_\beta$, since $a_\alpha b_\beta \in S_{\alpha\beta} \triangleq S_\gamma$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} a_\alpha b_\beta &= (i_\alpha, u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha)(i_\beta, u_\beta, \lambda_\beta) \\ &= (i_\alpha i_\beta, u_\alpha u_\beta, \lambda_\alpha \lambda_\beta) \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha, \gamma} i_\alpha i_\beta \varphi_{\beta, \gamma} i_\beta, 1_{U_\gamma} u_\alpha 1_{U_\gamma} u_\beta, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha, \gamma} \lambda_\alpha \lambda_\beta \psi_{\beta, \gamma} \lambda_\beta) \\ &= (i_\alpha \varphi_{\alpha, \gamma} i_\alpha, 1_{U_\gamma} u_\alpha, \lambda_\alpha \psi_{\alpha, \gamma} \lambda_\alpha)(i_\beta \varphi_{\beta, \gamma} i_\beta, 1_{U_\gamma} u_\beta, \lambda_\beta \psi_{\beta, \gamma} \lambda_\beta) \\ &= (a_\alpha \Phi_{\alpha, \gamma})(b_\beta \Phi_{\beta, \gamma}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, summing up the above discussions, $S(U)$ is isomorphic to a strong semilattice of rectangular monoids $S_\alpha(U_\alpha)$, that is, $S(U) = [Y; S_\alpha(U_\alpha); \Phi_{\alpha, \beta}]$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) The proof is similar with the corresponding (ii) \Rightarrow (iii) of Lemma 2.3.

For any $\alpha \in Y$, assume that $S_\alpha(U_\alpha) = I_\alpha \times T_\alpha \times \Lambda_\alpha$. Then, it is not hard to see that for any $(i, x, \lambda) \in S_\alpha, (j, y, \mu) \in S_\beta$, $(i, x, \lambda) \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U(j, y, \mu)$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$ and $\lambda = \mu \in \Lambda_\alpha$. On the other hand, if $(i, x, \lambda) \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U(j, y, \lambda)$ for some $\lambda \in \Lambda_\alpha$, then for all $(k, z, \nu) \in S_\gamma (\nu \in Y)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (i, 1_{T_\alpha}, \lambda)(k, z, \nu) &= (k', z', \nu') \in S_{\alpha\gamma}, \\ (i, x, \lambda)(k', 1_{T_{\alpha\gamma}}, \nu') &= (i', x', \lambda'), \\ (j, y, \lambda)(k', 1_{T_{\alpha\gamma}}, \nu') &= (j', y', \lambda''), \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, by using the above relations, we derive that

$$\begin{aligned} (i, x, \lambda)(k, z, \nu) &= (i, x, \lambda)(i, 1_{T_\alpha}, \lambda)(k, z, \nu) = (i, x, \lambda)(k', z', \nu') = (i, x, \lambda)(k', 1_{T_{\alpha\gamma}}, \nu')(k', z', \nu') \\ &= (i', x', \lambda')(k', z', \nu') = (i', x' z', \lambda'); \\ (j, y, \lambda)(k, z, \nu) &= (j, y, \lambda)(i, 1_{T_\alpha}, \lambda)(k, z, \nu) = (j, y, \lambda)(k', z', \nu') = (j, y, \lambda)(k', 1_{T_{\alpha\gamma}}, \nu')(k', z', \nu') \\ &= (j', y', \lambda'')(k', z', \nu') = (j', y' z', \lambda''). \end{aligned}$$

Thereby, we obtain that $(i, x, \lambda)(k, z, \nu) \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U(j, y, \lambda)(k, z, \nu)$ so that $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U$ is a right congruence on S .

Similarly, we can show that $(i, x, \lambda) \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U(j, y, \lambda)$ if and only if $i = j \in I_\alpha$ for some $\alpha \in Y$, and so $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U$ is a left congruence on S .

Hence, together with Lemma 2.3, $S(U)$ is a U-semi-superabundant semigroup satisfying the (C) condition for some $U \subseteq E(S)$. Note that U is a normal band of S , (iii) holds.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) The proof is similar with the corresponding (iii) \Rightarrow (i) of Lemma 2.3.

Assume that (iii) holds. Then, by Lemma 2.1, $S(U)$ is Smarandache U -liberal semigroup and for all $a \in S(U)$, $a_U^\circ = a_U^\circ$. Since $S(U)$ satisfies the (C) condition, we have, for all $a, b \in S(U)$,

$$(ab)_U^\circ \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U ab \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U ab \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U (ab)_U^\circ \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U ab \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U ab \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U a_U^\circ b_U^\circ.$$

This leads to $(ab)_U^\circ \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U (ab)_U^\circ \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U a_U^\circ b_U^\circ$. By Lemma 2.1 (i), we will get $(ab)_U^\circ \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^U (ab)_U^\circ \tilde{\mathcal{L}}^U a_U^\circ b_U^\circ$. Consequently, $(ab)_U^\circ = (ab)_U^\circ \mathcal{D} a_U^\circ b_U^\circ = a_U^\circ b_U^\circ$ holds. This shows that $S(U)$ satisfies the ET-condition. Note that U is a normal band of S , (i) holds.

Now, if we let $U = E(S)$ in Theorem 2.4, then we immediately have the following corollary.

Corollary 2.5. The following statements are equivalent for a semigroup S :

(i) $S(U)$ is a normal orthodox $E(S)$ -liberal semigroup;

(ii) $S(U)$ is a strong semilattice of some rectangular monoids, i.e., $S = [Y; S_\alpha(E(S_\alpha)); \Phi_{\alpha,\beta}]$, where $S_\alpha(E(S_\alpha))$ is a rectangular monoid for every $\alpha \in Y$ and $E(S)$ is a normal band of S .

(iii) $S(U)$ is a semi-superabundant semigroup satisfying the (C) condition, and $E(S)$ is a normal band of S .

In the above corollary, if we restrict the semigroup S to the abundant or regular semigroups, then it is not hard for us to get

Corollary 2.6. The following statements are equivalent for a semigroup S :

- (i) S is a normal orthocrypto semigroup;
- (ii) S is a strong semilattice of rectangular cancellative monoids, i.e., $S = [Y; S_\alpha; \Phi_{\alpha,\beta}]$, where $S_\alpha = I_\alpha \times T_\alpha \times \Lambda_\alpha$, and I_α is a left zero band, Λ_α is a right zero band, T_α is a cancellative monoid for every $\alpha \in Y$.

Corollary 2.7. The following statements are equivalent for a semigroup S :

- (i) S is a normal orthocryptogroup;
- (ii) S is a strong semilattice of rectangular groups.

Hence, our main result generalizes and extends some corresponding results on normal orthocryptou semigroups and normal orthocryptogroups.

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